

Project no.:

763959

Project acronym:

MegaRoller

Project full title:

**Developing the PTO of the first MW-level
Oscillating Wave Surge Converter**

Collaborative project

H2020-LCE-2017-RES-RIA-TwoStage

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Duration: 36 Months (3 years)

D6.7

Communication report I

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

MEGAROLLER MID-WAY COMMUNICATION STATUS

MegaRoller is a project with funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No 763959. The project shall develop and demonstrate a Power Take-Off for wave energy converters.

The communication plan applies to external communication and public outreach of results in the project.

The report gives a status of the external communication activities that have taken place in the consortium since project start and how this relates the activities set out in the corresponding communication plan. This document therefore contains an updated version of the original communication plan (D6.1) as well as the report on the activities taken place in the first 18 Months.

In the original communication plan, the project planned to make one final video. We found video for this project relevant and that it gives high visibility. Thus, we have already produced a video with views exceeding the KPIs. We are also producing several more videos that will be published in the last half of the project. The project is also on track on blogs, press releases and media. The media reach has exceeded the KPIs in the project.

1 MEGAROLLER WEBSITE

Figure 1.1: Snapshot of the MegaRoller website

The MegaRoller website is continuously updated with all recent reports, articles, white papers, innovations, blogposts and events, making them easily accessible to stakeholders. The project has a goal of 2000 web-sessions by the end of year 3. Currently (month 18) the website has had 1231 sessions, which is slightly ahead of schedule.

It is worth noting that as the website will have more content (e.g. papers, innovations, blogpost, videos) further along, it is expected that the number of sessions increase at a faster rate through the final 18 months than the first 18 months, meaning the project might even surpass its goal.

Below is an overview of the most viewed pages on the MegaRoller website. We are glad to see that the News-page is the most popular, indicating MegaRoller stakeholders are interested in the progress of the project. Also, partners, the internal pages and the front page get a lot of attention.

Side	Sidevisninger	Unike sidevisninger	Gj.sn. tid på side	Innganger	Faktfrekvens	% Utgang	Sideverdi
	1 231 <small>% av summen: 0,18 % (687 344)</small>	962 <small>% av summen: 0,18 % (527 113)</small>	00:01:14 <small>Gj.sn. for datautvalget: 00:01:34 (-21,06 %)</small>	543 <small>% av summen: 0,20 % (270 549)</small>	49,45 % <small>Gj.sn. for datautvalget: 55,27 % (-10,53 %)</small>	43,95 % <small>Gj.sn. for datautvalget: 39,36 % (11,65 %)</small>	USD 0,00 <small>% av summen: 0,00 % (USD 0,00)</small>
1. /projectweb/megaroller/news/	317 (25,75 %)	242 (25,16 %)	00:01:04	157 (28,91 %)	40,76 %	41,96 %	USD 0,00 (0,00 %)
2. /projectweb/megaroller/partners/	252 (20,47 %)	200 (20,79 %)	00:00:47	108 (19,89 %)	46,30 %	34,13 %	USD 0,00 (0,00 %)
3. /projectweb/megaroller/internal-pages/	229 (18,60 %)	188 (19,54 %)	00:01:51	112 (20,63 %)	77,68 %	59,83 %	USD 0,00 (0,00 %)
4. /projectweb/megaroller/	206 (16,73 %)	155 (16,11 %)	00:01:16	102 (18,78 %)	50,00 %	48,54 %	USD 0,00 (0,00 %)
5. /projectweb/megaroller/dissemination/	147 (11,94 %)	109 (11,33 %)	00:01:27	41 (7,55 %)	16,67 %	39,46 %	USD 0,00 (0,00 %)
6. /projectweb/megaroller/news/megaroller-kick-off/	54 (4,39 %)	48 (4,99 %)	00:01:04	17 (3,13 %)	47,06 %	42,59 %	USD 0,00 (0,00 %)
7. /projectweb/megaroller/events/	20 (1,62 %)	16 (1,66 %)	00:01:42	2 (0,37 %)	50,00 %	10,00 %	USD 0,00 (0,00 %)
8. /projectweb/megaroller	3 (0,24 %)	2 (0,21 %)	00:01:27	2 (0,37 %)	0,00 %	0,00 %	USD 0,00 (0,00 %)
9. /projectweb/megaroller)	2 (0,16 %)	1 (0,10 %)	00:27:39	1 (0,18 %)	0,00 %	50,00 %	USD 0,00 (0,00 %)
10. /projectweb/megaroller/?fbclid=IwAR0t9uvex3psdg_gpztthiz7mvr5gmkerww1m8b4rlg9mgtabkejmjzgcocm	1 (0,08 %)	1 (0,10 %)	00:00:00	1 (0,18 %)	100,00 %	100,00 %	USD 0,00 (0,00 %)

Figure 1.2: Snapshot of MegaRoller website statistics (Google Analytics) in Norwegian. The most relevant columns are (From the left.) nr. 1: site url/name, nr. 2: page views, nr 3: unique page views, nr 4: av. time spent on page

2 BLOG

Blogposts on the SINTEFBlog are an excellent way to increase reach of scientific publications and important project events. The blog has approx. 10 000 monthly readers, and blogs are easily shared in social media and newsletters. MegaRoller's strategy is to write a blogpost based on all scientific publication and innovation. MegaRoller will also present a summary of every workshop as a blogpost.

By year 2, the goal is 3 blogposts on the SINTEFblog. By month 18 MegaRoller already has 4 blogposts; One scientific blogpost and two workshop summaries and a summary from the Kick-off meeting. They have 295 views combined.

Figure 2.1: Snapshot of MegaRoller website statistics (Google Analytics) in Norwegian. The most relevant columns are (From the left.) nr. 1: site url/name, nr. 2: page views, nr 3: unique page views, nr 4: av. time spent on page

Figure 2.2: Snapshot of MegaRoller blogs – kick-off meeting og workshop summary

Moving forward, MegaRoller will continue to publish blogposts from workshops and scientific publications. In addition to publishing the blogposts on the SINTEFblog, SINTEF Energy Research's social media as well as social media of relevant partners should be utilized to maximize reach. Read more on this in the "Social media and videos" section.

3 PRESS RELEASES

In year 1 the project had two press releases, meaning the we are on track. The first was released by MegaRoller partner K2 Management (left), the second by MegaRoller partner AW Energy (right).

Figure 3.1: Snapshot of MegaRoller the two press releases from AW-Energy

4 MEDIA

MegaRoller has a goal of two news stories with a potential reach of 150 000 people, by the end of year 2. By month 18, three news stories with an accumulated potential reach of (at least) 165 000 people has been released, meaning we have already reached our target.

One news story, on the potential for wave energy in Norway, Portugal and Ireland, was in the Norwegian magazine *Teknisk Ukeblad*, with 150 000 potential readers.

Figure 4.1: Snapshot from Teknisk Ukeblad

The second news story was about project completing the WEC model. It was published on the news-site *Marine Energy Biz*, with 15.000 potential readers

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 763959.

MegaRoller Project Reaches New Milestone

Photo: K2 Management

MegaRoller project has reached a milestone by completing an advanced custom structure interaction Wave Energy Converter (WEC) model.

The MegaRoller project is an EU-funded research program over the period 2018-2021. The project will develop and demonstrate a 1 MW power take-off (PTO) for wave energy converters.

The PTO is developed in conjunction with oscillating wave surge converters (OWSCs), a class of wave power technology that uses bottom-hinged plates oscillating in pitch following the surge movement of the water particles in the nearshore zone.

Figure 4.2: Snapshot from "Marine Energy Biz".

The third news story, also on the WEC model, was published on the news-site *Power Technology*. Potential number of readers is unknown.

20 MARCH 2019 NEWS

EU MegaRoller wave energy project completes model phase

By Jack Unwin

SHARE

The EU wave energy project MegaRoller has completed a Wave Energy Converter (WEC) model to develop wave energy systems. Credit: AW-Energy Oy

RECOMMENDED COMPANIES

- Skrivanek**
Skrivanek is a global translation company with more than two...
- BarkerBille**
BarkerBille designs and manufactures a variety of highly efficient fans...
- SIFCO ASC**
SIFCO Applied Surface Concepts (SIFCO ASC) is the global leader...

SPONSORED FINANCIAL CONTENT

What are the benefits of infrastructure investment companies?

Figure 4.3: Snapshot from Power Technology.

5 NEWSLETTER

The goal is to send out newsletters to ensure that those who set the framework for MegaRoller, the industry, stakeholders and partners are updated on the latest activities and results.

The external MegaRoller newsletter has been delayed. The goal to establish a newsletter with 100 subscribers. The newsletter mailing list will be established by SINTEF Energy Research. To gain as many subscribers as possible, all partners are responsible for marketing the newsletter in their own communication channels.

MegaRoller has sent out an internal newsletter to partners in year one.

Figure 5.1: Snapshot from MegaRoller internal newsletter

6 SOCIAL MEDIA AND VIDEO

A key activity to create visibility and engagement in the field of wave energy (within the scope of MegaRoller), is to produce videos for social media, targeting the wave energy industry. The videos will in large be produced using on-site interviews from work-package leaders and partners in the project. They will promote activities, innovations and visibility within areas where MegaRoller has leading experts internationally.

By the end of year 2, the goal is to have four videos. At this point (month 18) one video (from a site visit in Portugal) has been published. The video presents the MegaRoller projects, its objective and its potential impact.

Figure 6.1: Snapshot of Portugal site visit video post on SINTEF Energy Research's Facebook

Five videos, presenting each work package (WP 1 and 2 are in the same video as they have the same WP-leader) in detail are ready for publication. Four additional videos are in production, featuring individual partners (ABB, Hydroll, Hydman and AW-Energy) and their contribution to MegaRoller.

SINTEF Energy's (who is responsible for communication and dissemination) social media channels were used to publish the first video. As can be seen from the table below, it accumulated 3400 views across all channels, meaning the goal of 2500 total views was substantially surpassed by this video alone.

Video name	Facebook	Instagram	Twitter	LinkedIn	YouTube	Total
Site visit in Portugal	1400	150	300	1500	40	3400

For the upcoming videos, other partners' social media channels will also be used actively to maximize MegaRoller's reach and target even more relevant audiences. The videos featuring the WPs will be published on the MegaRoller website by the end of year 2. Also, all partners will share the video for the WP(s) they are involved in, in their social media, newsletter and other relevant channels. The partner-videos will be published in late year 2/early year 3. They will be put on the website and the social media channels of the partner featured in the video and SINTEF Energy Research.

The new story from *Teknisk ukeblad* (See "Media and press releases") has also been shared through SINTEF Energy Research's Facebook page. 2400 people were reached by the post. An additional 2000 were reached through publishing it on SINTEF Energy Research's Twitter account.

Figure 6.2: Snapshot of Social media posts on Facebook and twitter. 1930 views on twitter, and 22 interactions.

Combining video views and people reached by the above-mentioned tweet and Facebook-post, MegaRoller has 7 800 views in social media. The goal by the end of year 3 all three is 20 000 views, which is well within reach with the nine videos coming up. There will also be an increased focus on sharing news stories and blogposts in social media.

Below are pictures of the Portugal site visit video and its view-statistics across all social media channels.

Figure 6.3: Snapshot of Portugal site visit video on SINTEF Energy Research's Instagram account.

6.1 Facebook & Instagram

Figure 6.4: Snapshot of Statistics of Portugal site visit video on SINTEF Energy Research's Facebook account which shows 1400 views.

6.2 Twitter

Figure 6.5: Snapshot of video statistic from SINTEF Energy Research's Twitter account, 212 views.

The video was published two times on Twitter for better reach.

Figure 6.6: Snapshot of Twitter statistics second time it was published, 90 views.

6.3 LinkedIn

Engasjement for oppdateringer										Vis: 10
Oppdater tittel	Lagt ut av	Opprettet	Eksponeringer	Videovisninger	Klikk	CTR	Reaksjoner	Kommentarer	Deling	
Utvikling av fremtidens kraftsystem Alle følgere	Arne Steenstru...	12.6.2019	1 063	-	41	3,86 %	9	0		
SINTEF deltar sammen med norsk kraftbransje på RENs Metodedager L... Alle følgere	Christoffer Solberg	12.6.2019	1 118	-	12	1,07 %	7	0		
Forskere til avdeling Gassteknologi Alle følgere	Arne Steenstru...	11.6.2019	664	-	26	3,92 %	0	0		
Maskinen som spiser alt! Gassifiseringsreaktoren på SINTEF Energy... Alle følgere	John-Ivar F. Eldsmo	7.6.2019	3 016	949	51	1,69 %	39	0		
Mye tyder på at det er en fornyet glød for havvind. Ser vi begynnelsen på en ny giv f... Alle følgere	Christoffer Solberg	5.6.2019	1 615	-	30	1,86 %	15	0		
SINTEF participates in an exciting Wave Energy project developing the next... Alle følgere	John-Ivar F. Eldsmo	4.6.2019	1 218	324	16	1,31 %	4	0		

Figure 6.7: Snapshot of LinkedIn views, 1218 views.

The video was published two times on LinkedIn for better reach.

Engasjement for oppdateringer										Vis: 10
Oppdater tittel	Eksponeringer	Videovisninger	Klikk	CTR	Reaksjoner	Kommentarer	Delinger	Følgere	Engasjement	
Utvikling av fremtidens kraftsystem Alle følgere	1 063	-	41	3,86 %	9	0	2	-	4,89 %	
SINTEF deltar sammen med norsk kraftbransje på RENs Metodedager L... Alle følgere	1 118	-	12	1,07 %	7	0	0	-	1,7 %	
Forskere til avdeling Gassteknologi Alle følgere	664	-	26	3,92 %	0	0	0	-	3,92 %	
Maskinen som spiser alt! Gassifiseringsreaktoren på SINTEF Energy... Alle følgere	3 016	949	51	1,69 %	39	0	1	-	3,02 %	
Mye tyder på at det er en fornyet glød for havvind. Ser vi begynnelsen på en ny giv f... Alle følgere	1 615	-	30	1,86 %	15	0	1	-	2,85 %	
SINTEF participates in an exciting Wave Energy project developing the next... Alle følgere	1 218	324	16	1,31 %	4	0	1	-	1,72 %	

Figure 6.8: Snapshot of Portugal site visit video on SINTEF Energy Research's LinkedIn-account, 324 views.

6.4 Youtube

Figure 6.9: Snapshot of Portugal site visit video post on SINTEF Energy Research's YouTube.

7 COMMUNICATION KPIS AND CURRENT NUMBERS

Track	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	KPI	Status Communicaton M18
Social media campaigns (through partners channels)	Twitter LinkedIn Facebook	Twitter LinkedIn Facebook	Twitter LinkedIn Facebook	Social media views in total: 20000	7800 views
Project video: YouTube Social Media channels		4 videos	4 videos	Total views: 2500	7800
Blogs	3 blogs	3 blogs	3 blogs	Blog views: 1000	4 blogs 295 views
Press releases	Press release 1 Press release 2	Press release 3	Press release 4	Total PR coverage (incl. online articles) = 800 press hits	2
Newsletter MailPoet/hosted by #SINTEFenergy blog	1 newsletters	2 newsletters	2 newsletters	100 subscribers	1
Media/Cordis wire service	1 story	2 story	2 story	Potential views: 150 000	3 stories 165000
Webpages	Share deliverables/ events/ results	Share deliverables/ events/ results	Share deliverables/ events/ results	Views 2 000	1231

Figure 7.1: Communication KPI's from updated communication plan together with M18 status

8 UPDATED COMMUNICATION PLAN MEGAROLLER

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

MegaRoller is a project with funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No 763959. The project shall develop and demonstrate a Power Take-Off for wave energy converters.

This communication plan applies to external communication and public outreach of results in the project.

Good external communication shall contribute to MegaRoller becoming a successful project:

- MegaRoller will actively communicate innovations, research, knowledge and project results to raise the level of awareness and knowledge about wave energy, and specifically MegaRoller's specific contributions in this area.

The communication plan is based on the principle of pro-active communication, where activities are strategically planned, and the communication process is illustrated and elaborated through the figure shown below.

9 COMMUNICATION FRAMEWORK AND OBJECTIVES

9.1 Background

MegaRoller is funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No 763959. The project shall develop and demonstrate a Power Take-Off for wave energy converters with the following characteristics;

- Increased performance
- Increased reliability
- Decreased costs
- Improved power quality

In the long term a potential 40 000 MW roll-out of MegaRoller power plants can generate 400 000 jobs by 2050 and save 110 Million tons per year in CO₂ emissions in Europe alone.

Open and engaging communication of project results is a strategic activity in MegaRoller and an integral part of the management's responsibility. Communication will extend beyond the MegaRoller consortium to provide knowledge about wave energy and promote innovations and investments to industry.

This communication plan applies to external communication and public outreach, information about the project and results in the project.

Project internal communication is covered in the deliverable "D7.2: Project management plan" and in the deliverable "D8.1: Project coordination plan" (communication to EU).

Collaboration activities such as workshops and industry conferences will be addressed in more detail in D6.3 Dissemination Plan, however these are relevant activities to communicate and are therefore listed in the communication activity timeline (table 7.1).

10 COMMUNICATION PRINCIPLES

This communication plan is based on a principle of pro-active communication, where activities are strategically planned, and not an ad hoc activity. The communication process is illustrated with this figure:

Figure 10.1: Illustration of the different steps in a communication activity and questions that needs to be answered in order to achieve the desired impact. This communication plan is also structured according to these steps.

The steps are in line with the advice given on the H2020 Participant Portal on good communication in projects: (http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/grants/grant-management/communication_en.htm).

- Why: Set clear communication objectives, and the intended impact.
- Who: Who do you need to communicate to in order to have an impact? Who are the stakeholders?
- What: What do you need to say so that the target group understands the message and become engaged?
- How: What channels are the most efficient in order to reach the intended target group?

11 WHY: COMMUNICATION GOAL AND KPI'S

11.1 MegaRoller Communication Goal

Good external communication shall contribute to MegaRoller becoming a successful project.

MegaRoller should actively communicate innovations, research, knowledge and project results, and the project specific contributions to:

- *raise the level of awareness and knowledge* about wave energy and its contribution to job creation and as a climate-friendly energy source
- *promote innovations and investment* to industry

11.2 MegaRoller Communication KPI's

MegaRoller Communication KPIs and impact are listed in the *Table 11.1* below. For more detailed communication activity timeline see table 7.1.

Table 11.1: MegaRoller Communication KPIs

Track	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	KPI
Social media campaigns (through partners channels)	Twitter LinkedIn Facebook	Twitter LinkedIn Facebook	Twitter LinkedIn Facebook	Social media views in total: 20000
Project video: YouTube Social Media channels		4 videos	4 videos	Total views: 2500
Blogs	3 blogs	3 blogs	3 blogs	Blog views: 1000
Press releases	Press release 1 Press release 2	Press release 3	Press release 4	Total PR coverage (incl. online articles) = 800 press hits
Newsletter MailPoet/hosted by #SINTEEnergy blog	1 newsletters	2 newsletters	2 newsletters	100 subscribers
Media/Cordis wire service	1 story	2 story	2 story	Potential views: 150 000
Webpages	Share deliverables/ events/results	Share deliverables/ events/results	Share deliverables/ events/results	Views 2 000

12 WHO: AUDIENCES/STAKEHOLDERS FOR COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES

Government agencies, organizations and individuals have different relationships to MegaRoller. An analysis of these audiences will provide answers to: Who is important to us, and to whom are we important? Who can influence us, and whom can we influence?

Figure 12.1 Communication chart MegaRoller

12.1.1 Explanation of the Communication Chart

Those who define the framework

Parties who have formal authority to decide directly on political and economic objectives as well as the framework for the organization, or who, through their decisions, will indirectly influence the activities.

Those who are directly involved

Parties associated with day-to-day activities who have a key role in performing the organization's tasks.

Those who have ad hoc interests

Parties who have an interest in specific cases or situations in our activities or certain aspects of a complex issue. Examples of such parties include media, professional interest organizations, activist groups, individuals.

Those who have industry knowledge

Parties who influence industry standards relevant to the activities. These may be research international organizations, institutions and professional groups. We can also include organizations that are or have been in the same situation as the project has.

12.1.2 External contact list

The project will create a contact list of key stakeholders list with organisations and individuals expressing interest and consenting to receiving information about the project. They will be added to the list in a way that is GDPR compliant through:

- signing for the MegaRoller newsletter through the #SINTEFenergy-blog
- sending an enquiry through the project website
- contacting the project partners at workshops, events etc.

13 WHAT: MESSAGES

Key messages in the MegaRoller project will support the message of the European Energy Union:

A European energy union will ensure that Europe has secure, affordable and climate-friendly energy. Wiser energy use while fighting climate change is both a spur for new jobs and growth and an investment in Europe's future. (https://ec.europa.eu/commission/priorities/energy-union-and-climate_en)

A key message in MegaRoller is therefore the projects contribution as a low carbon technology and to job-creation:

- In the long term a 40 000 MW roll-out of MegaRoller power plants can generate 400 000 jobs by 20150 and save 110 M tons/years in CO2 emissions in Europe only.

There are four key *areas* of communication in the MegaRoller project:

1. **Activities:** communicate the activities (workshops, conferences etc) in the project, and what the project has achieved
2. **Innovation:** communicate innovative solutions from MegaRoller project
3. **Research:** communicate Peer-reviewed-articles and project results (e.g. technical reports)
4. **Wave energy - experts/commentator role:** work to promote visibility within areas where MegaRoller are leading experts internationally.

14 HOW: MEASURES AND CHANNELS

14.1 Communication activities in MegaRoller – who is responsible?

Communication, public outreach and participation in the public debate in an integral part of the management responsibility.

- **Management** is responsible for providing the *foundation* for and *quality assurance* of project communication.
- Each **WP leader** is responsible for *initiating communication and providing summaries and popularised version* of their specific contribution to the project.
- **WP6 and project management** has a responsibility to *ensure frequency and quality* of the external communication.

14.2 MegaRoller visual identity

All projects hosted and/or funded by MegaRoller shall follow MegaRoller graphic profile for e.g. websites, brochures and presentations. The information to the public will be provided in a uniform way for a wider visibility of the work done in the MegaRoller project.

The project logo is together with the EU-flag an intrinsic part of the publication and presentation layouts of the MegaRoller project.

Figure 14.1: MegaRoller project logos

All logos will also be published also with negative coloured versions for use on dark backgrounds. The logos are available for participants through the MegaRoller internal communication platform (SharePoint).

The MegaRoller logo consist of a wave included in the letter M. This M is, so far, used in three versions:

- MegaRoller symbol.
- MegaRoller vertical logo.
- MegaRoller horizontal logo.

14.3 Priority MegaRoller channels

The priority MegaRoller Communication channels to reach the target groups in the most efficient way are:

- Webpages
- Blogs from #SINTEFblog
- Newsletter
- Press releases
- Media/Cordis Wire Service (popular media and tech/science media)
- Social media – LinkedIn and Twitter (supported by partner's established social media channels)
- Project video on Youtube and all other relevant channels above

A specific channel will be selected based on the communications need and suitable channel for the purpose. The following is a description of each of these channels.

14.3.1 Website

The MegaRoller website has been launched at www.MegaRoller.eu . The host address is www.sintef.no/MegaRoller, where all public reports/deliverables, events and articles will be shared to stimulate communication. The website will also host white papers developed to promote the technology. A partner-restricted SharePoint site hosted by SINTEF is established for project internal communication and collaboration.

The content for the website are editable by the communication department at SINTEF Energy Research.

The Public website includes:

- About the project
- Participants
- News
- Results/Videos/Blogs
- Work packages
- Link to internal pages (sharepoint)

The graphical layout of the Web page for MegaRoller is shown in the screen capture shown in Figure 14.2

Figure 14.2: Screen capture from the project website MegaRoller.eu in June 2018

- Goal: To have dynamic and always updated websites
- A link to all recent open publications and innovations should be on the front page
- Contact information should always be updated
- Updated info about seminars and conferences organized by MegaRoller – through the blog
- Responsible for content: All partners

14.3.2 Blog: #SINTEFblog

- Goal: A summary of every scientific publication and innovation as blogs, a summary of every workshop should be blogged about.
- Blogs should be signed by individual contributor, but MegaRoller must be mentioned
- Responsible: All partners to contribute, blog is published and edited by WP6 participants

14.3.3 Newsletter

- Goal: Send out newsletters approx. every six months to ensure that those who set the framework for MegaRoller, the industry, stakeholders and partners are updated
- Responsible: WP6 with input from all.

14.3.4 Press releases

- The consortium will issue press releases at key milestones in the project
- Responsible: MegaRoller management with support from WP6

14.3.5 Media/Cordis wire service

- Goal: MegaRoller should have minimum one media story every year and use the CORDIS Wire service for major project result announcements.
- The project will target the mainstream media in Europe to raise public awareness about the direct benefits the project can bring to them in terms of job creation and cleaner energy.
- Assess each scientific article to see if it is suitable for a media story
- Responsible: Coordinated by the project management and WP6, all partners must contribute with content.

14.3.6 Social Media (SoMe)

- Goal: Create visibility and engagement in the field of wave energy (within the scope of MegaRoller)
- Existing social media (Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook etc. Press releases on all relevant channels above)
- Press releases on all relevant channels above and company blogs will be used to disseminate key news and white papers, and to attract further commercial and industrial partners to the ecosystem, promote the user association, attract further commercial and industrial partners, and to foster a wider discussion of the topic of ocean energy and breakthrough WEC technology.
- Responsible: Co-ordinated by WP6, contributions from all

14.3.7 Videos

- The consortium will also produce project videos targeting the wave energy industry. The videos will in large be produced using on-site interviews from work package leaders and partners in the project.

15 MEGAROLLER COMMUNICATION ACTIVITY TIMELINE

The timeline below is indicative of the activities planned in the project, and this timeline is dynamic as the project is developed.

Table 15.1: MegaRoller Communication Activity Timeline.

Project Month	Calendar Month	Activity	Communication activity
M1	Apr/May.18	MegaRoller Kick-off meeting	Press release (published April 18) Launch of website and visual identity News item - Distribution to SoMe and website
M2	Jun.18	ICOE conference 2018	News item - Distribution to SoMe and website
M3	Jul.18		
M4	Aug.18		
M5	Sep.18	MegaRoller Kick-off meeting	News item - Distribution to SoMe and website
M6	Oct.18	Project milestone: Wave-Structure Interaction Model Ready	Press release - Distribution to press, some and website OR Blog Media/Cordis story
M7	Nov.18		
M8	Dec.18		
M9	Jan.19		
M10	Feb.19		
M11	Mar.19		
M12	Apr.19	MegaRoller General Assembly meeting: Portugal	News item - Distribution to SoMe and website
M13	May 19	Project internal site visit Portugal	Video about project published
M14	Jun.19		
M15	Jul.19		
M16	Aug.19		
M17	Sep.19	EWTEC conference; MegaRoller External Advisory Board Meeting	News item - Distribution to SoMe and website
M18	Okt.19	Project milestone: PTO Design Ready; World Energy Congress; Offshore Energy Exhibiton & Conference	Press release - distribution to press, SoMe and website AND Blog Media/Cordis story
M19	Nov.19	WP interviews	5 WP videos published
M20	Dec.19	EU Periodic Review	

M21	Jan.20	Internal site visit Finland	4 videos posted
M22	Feb.20		
M23	Mar.20		
M24	Apr.20	Project milestone: PTO Subsystems Ready; MegaRoller General Assembly Meeting in Norway	Press release - distribution to press, SoMe and website AND Blog
M25	May 20		
M26	Jun.20	ICOE Conference 2020	Blog and / or news item - distribution SoMe and website
M27	Jul.20	Project milestone: PTO Assembly Ready	Press release - distribution to press, SoMe and website AND Blog
M28	Aug.20		
M29	Sep.20	MegaRoller workshop: WEC and renewable energy technology developers interested in technology transfer	Blog and / or news item - distribution SoMe and website
M30	Oct.20	Offshore Energy Exhibiton & Conference	Blog and / or news item - distribution SoMe and website
M31	Nov.20	MegaRoller External Advisory Board meeting	Blog and / or news item - distribution SoMe and website
M32	Des.20	MegaRoller workshop: potential customers, members of standards working groups, government representatives and press	
M33	Jan.21	Project milestone: PTO Validation Completed	Press release - Distribution to press, SoMe and website
M34	Feb.21	MegaRoller General Assembly meeting: Finland (Järvenpää)	News item - Distribution to SoMe and website Media/Cordis story
M35	Mar.21		Project video
M36	Apr.21	Project milestone: All dissemination, exploitation and standardization activities completed	
		EU End of Project review	

16 EVALUATION

Communication efforts will be evaluated and reported continuously, and systematic feedback will form the basis for regular revision of the communication plan.

The evaluation of communication activities is based on the following:

- Feedback received in the daily work should be reported to WP6 so that necessary adjustments can be undertaken. Responsible: All project participants
- Conduct a meeting with the Management in each year, to review and evaluate recent years communication activities. Responsible: WP6 and MegaRoller management
- Statistics of hits on websites. Responsible: WP6

17 LIST OF INTERNAL STAKEHOLDERS IN MEGAROLLER

Table 17.1: MegaRoller Internal Stakeholder contact list.

This list is in the original plan, but due to GDPR this list with emails cannot be shared in an open report.